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D6.1 Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

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Grant Agreement No.: 101091933	

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EU-RES	Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

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Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable, D6.1 “*Plan for communication & stakeholder engagement strategy & plan and promotion of the open call*”, released at Month 3, describes the main objectives and expected outcomes of the communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities to be adopted and deployed during the first projects’ year, the methodology and assets behind the strategy and the envisaged set of actions for the timeframe M1-M12 and beyond, to ensure the successful achievement of the project objectives in terms of appropriate dissemination of main results and outputs, community building endeavours, open calls’ promotion and project recognition.

This plan lays the basis of our foundation to draw on the best practices that worked during the pilot project StandICT.eu [2018-2020] and StandICT.eu 2023 coordinated by Trust-IT, and take these lessons learned to then become an integral part of our communication and stakeholder’s engagement strategy plan for StandICT.eu 2026.

The plan will be shaped and executed following the primary goals defined as follows:

- (i) Increase the outreach of the voice of European ICT Standards experts that are tangibly contributing into SDOs and Standards development in critical ICTs’ areas, through the Open Calls.
- (ii) As a critical lesson learned from previous initiatives, we shall augment and intensify collaborations with the SME bodies organisations and Public Private Partnerships (PPPs).
- (iii) Support the realisation and dissemination of the European ICT Standardisation Observatory (EUOS) outputs, especially through the “Landscape of Analysis reports”, as important elements for the community to exhaustively perform a Standards gap analysis and providing a Standards impact assessment, to be fed into future and correlated policies and regulations.
- (iv) Maintain and enrich the cooperation channel with the EC Multi Stakeholder Platform (MSP), as a valuable and relevant community for StandICT.eu and the plan addresses ideas to have the MSP engage better with the project and for them to draw value from the StandICT.eu services.
- (v) Transform both the EUOS and the Standards Training Academy in the “*go-to place*” for the ICT Standards community to not only to find relevant notions on any relevant gaps, priorities, challenges and Landscape analysis in topical Rollin Plans’ domains, but also to provide a place for effective discussion and exchange of information as well as to start learning the basics (and more) in Standardisation (covering the educational side). This is guaranteed thanks to role the External Advisory Group (EAG) members who will be chosen specifically as the right channel to feed the different topics.

Lastly, the project is planning and running one-on-one relations with specific organisations (ranging through the seven SGs) that can work as multipliers to their specific communities.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1. INTRODUCTION.....	10
1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE	10
1.2 STRUCTURE	11
1.3 RELATION WITH OTHER PROJECT DELIVERABLES	11
2. COMMUNICATION, ENGAGEMENT AND DISSEMINATION – THE BUILDING BLOCKS.....	12
2.1 OPEN CALLS & FELLOWSHIP PROGRAMME	12
2.2 EUOS OBSERVATORY AND TECHNICAL WORKING GROUPS.....	13
2.3 STANDICT.EU NETWORK & SYNERGIES.....	14
2.4 STANDARDS ACADEMY PROGRAMME – THE EDUCATIONAL SIDE	16
3. STAKEHOLDER GROUPS.....	18
3.1 NATIONAL STANDARD BODIES	18
3.2 EUROPEAN & INTERNATIONAL SDOs	18
3.3 SMEs	20
3.4 POLICY MAKERS	21
3.5 STANDARDS EDUCATION.....	21
3.6 OPEN SOURCE COMMUNITY	22
3.7 H2020, HORIZON EUROPE PROJECTS AND OTHER R&I INITIATIVES.....	23
4. OPEN CALL(S) PROMOTIONAL STRATEGY.....	25
4.1 OPEN CALL FOR EVALUATORS.....	25
4.2 OPEN CALL FOR APPLICANTS/EXPERTS.....	26
5. METHODOLOGY BEHIND THE COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND ENGAGEMENT PLAN.....	28
5.1 BRANDING AND VISUAL IDENTITY GUIDELINES	28
5.2 WEBINARS & WORKSHOPS.....	31
5.3 SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS	33
5.4 NEWSLETTERS.....	35
5.5 THIRD-PARTY EVENTS.....	36

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call	 <small>ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe</small>
Grant Agreement No.: 101091933	

5.6 TIMELINE OF ACTIVITIES (M1 – M12)..... 37

6. CONCLUSIONS..... 40

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1 - SNAPSHOT OF CURRENT STANDICT.EU NETWORK AND SYNERGIES.....	16
FIGURE 2 - OVERVIEW OF THE CURRENT NETWORK OF ENGAGED INTERNATIONAL, REGIONAL SDOS AND STANDARDISATION ORGANISATIONS.	20
FIGURE 3 - STANDICT.EU'S NETWORK OF EUROPEAN PROJECTS' SYNERGIES	24
FIGURE 4 – OFFICIAL BANNER OF EPE OPEN CALL.....	25
FIGURE 5 - FIRST OPEN CALL THEMATIC BANNER	27
FIGURE 6 - OFFICIAL STANDICT.EU & EUOS LOGOS	29
FIGURE 7 – DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE	30
FIGURE 8 – POWERPOINT PPT TEMPLATE	30
FIGURE 9 - PRESS RELEASE EXAMPLE FROM PROJECTS' KO MEETING.....	30
FIGURE 10 – PROMOTIONAL BANNER OF THE FIRST STANDICT.EU 2026'S WEBINAR ...	33
FIGURE 11 – EXAMPLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA LAYOUT TO SUPPORT PROMOTION OF SPECIFIC OUTPUTS.....	35
FIGURE 12 - EXAMPLE OF STANDICT.EU NEWSLETTER (FEBRUARY 2023 ISSUE)	36

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

ABBREVIATIONS

ACRONYM	Explanation
AUS	AUSTRALO Interinnov Marketing Lab
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CEN CENELEC	European Committee for electrotechnical Standardization
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DCU	Dublin City University
DEP	Digital Europe Programme
DSME	European Digital SME Alliance
EAG	External Advisory Group
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EUOS	European Observatory for ICT Standards
EUOS-SEG	EUOS Standards Education Group
EURAS	European Academy for Standardisation
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MSP	European Multi-Stakeholder Platform on ICT Standardisation
MSs	Member States
NSB	National Standard Bodies
OFE	OpenForum Europe
OSS	Open-Source Software
SGs	Stakeholder Groups
STAIR WG	STAndards, Innovation and Research Working Group
TWG	Technical Working Group

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

standICT.eu²⁰²⁶

ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This deliverable, D6.1 “*Plan for communication & stakeholder engagement strategy & plan and promotion of the open call*”, released at Month 3, describes the key goals, expected outcomes, methodologies and set of activities of the communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement plan to be adopted throughout the course of the project (M1-M36) of StandICT.eu 2026 to ensure the successful achievement of the Project objectives and to reach out the targeted Stakeholders. It also provides the roadmap for StandICT.eu Stakeholder engagement. The plan is meant to be leveraged as a living document: as no iterations are formally envisaged in the Grant Agreement, the Consortium ensures to properly handle any particular need or divergence that might be worthy to be implemented during its execution, as well as to consider the feasibility to produce a mid-term updated version, in case significant changes in the overall plan should be needed.

The StandICT.eu Communication and Engagement strategy will deploy a pragmatic and coordinated approach to successfully promote the project’s Open Calls and disseminate their outcomes using an extensive set of communication channels to target the broad and variegated network of Stakeholders involved.

This deliverable defines the different types of stakeholders identified, the engagement strategy devised for each of them and the modus operandi and tools to be adopted. These include communication activities at key events to facilitate outreach to the target research communities.

The specific objectives of the plan for Communication & Engagement of the Open Calls can be spelled out as follows:

1. Implement a branding and visual strategy to ensure the full recognition of the StandICT.eu project within the European and potentially international ICT Standards Community in full continuity with the previous Projects.
2. Deliver a strategic plan for Communication & Engagement to achieve the widest reach of the Open Calls to an appropriate audience and attract the most talented European ICT Standards Experts, with a view to maximise the size of top-quality applications submitted.
3. Showcase the most relevant StandICT.eu 2026’s results, creating awareness of the impact of the cascade funding and ensuring they contribute to the shaping of future European ICT Policies. Particularly, tailored outreach campaigns will be designed to further disseminate the results obtained by the different Technical Working Groups (TWG) through the release of the corresponding “*Landscape & Gap analysis reports*” as well as the dedicated “*Fellows Impact Reports*” to thoroughly showcase main the outputs of funded fellows.
4. Provide an accurate yet exhaustive description of the major targeted Stakeholders and the outreach strategy to be adopted to ensure continuing support of the project’s uptake through the establishment of solid partnerships.

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

1.2 Structure

The document is divided in the following sections:

- *Section 1* Introduction – Highlighting the high-level scope of the document as a reference for the overall Communication and Stakeholder Engagement strategy.
- *Section 2* Communication, Engagement and Dissemination – The Building Blocks – Providing an accurate description of the key-goals that will contribute to establish the StandICT.eu ecosystem.
- *Section 3* Stakeholder Groups – Listing the most significant project Stakeholders and a two-fold explanation on: 1) How they are going to be addressed and engaged and/or 2) How they will play a supportive role in the achievement of the project's objectives.
- *Section 4* Open Calls Promotional Strategy – This part contains a comprehensive list of the different channels, strategies and methodologies to be leveraged to ensure the broadest exposure and outreach of the project's Open Calls.
- *Section 5* Methodology behind the communication, dissemination and engagement plan – Showcasing the toolkit of Digital Channels, events and assets that will be exploited to bolster the promotion and dissemination of the project's results and the positioning of a recognisable and successful brand identity.
- *Section 6* - Conclusions

1.3 Relation with other project deliverables

The following StandICT.eu 2026 deliverables which are related to this document are the following:

- D3.1 Call monitoring report 1
- D3.2 Call monitoring report 2
- D3.3 Fellowship Programme interim report
- D3.4 Call monitoring report 3
- D3.5 Fellowship Programme final report
- D4.1 Standardisation Training Strategy
- D5.1 Stakeholder engagement midterm report
- D5.2 Stakeholder engagement final report

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

2. COMMUNICATION, ENGAGEMENT AND DISSEMINATION – THE BUILDING BLOCKS

2.1 OPEN CALLS & FELLOWSHIP PROGRAMME

StandICT.eu 2026 will deliver 9 Open Calls for proposals, the “The StandICT.eu Fellowship Programme”, the first of which will be issued in May 2023, via the customized StandICT.eu Grants Platform. Through a cascade grant mechanism, the Open Calls will provide a total of € 2,925,000 funding earmarked over 36 months with the ambitious objective to support participation and leadership of key EU specialists via expert collaboration in international ICT standard developing organisations, global fora and consortia, enabling them to contribute effectively to international ICT standards efforts.

The 9 Open Calls will primarily rely on the list of technological priority areas as listed in the recently released Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation 2023¹, and correlated supported policies.

The macro areas encompassed in the Rolling Plan (each one inclusive of multiple sub-categories) can be defined as follows:

1. Foundational Drivers
2. Key Enablers
3. Societal Challenges
4. Innovation for the Digital Single Market
5. Sustainable Growth

On top of this, the Consortium will monitor to ensure the timely inclusion of any relevant emerging Standardisation field through the supportive action of the External Advisory Group, the feedback coming from the funded fellows as well as through dedicated surveys aimed at gathering inputs from EU-funded projects in the frame of the Horizon Europe and Digital Europe Programme schemes.

The proposals addressing the specific topics of the call will be evaluated by three independent experts from the Project’s External Pool of Evaluators with the most successful retained for funding. Plus, we have introduced the roles of the rapporteur as well as an additional fourth expert who will be the final quality controller. Three types of proposals may be submitted:

- Long Term contributions (travel option included) with a maximum duration of six months and funding up to 10,000 Euro;
- Short Term contributions (travel option included) with a maximum duration of three months funding amount up to 5,000 Euro;

¹ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/rolling-plan-2023>

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

standICT.eu²⁰²⁶

ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

- One-Shot contributions to support participation at workshops or events (as active participant, presenter, convenor, chair/co-chair, observer etc..) and maximum funding of 3,000 Euro.

2.2 EUOS Observatory and Technical Working Groups

The European Observatory for ICT Standards (EUOS) will expand the current repository to include more detailed publishable metadata of standards and, most importantly, will strengthen and improve the realisation of new “*Landscape Analysis Reports*”

The objective to be attained before Project completion is to offer an exhaustive coverage of all major SDOs operating globally and of all significant ICT standards, with a particular focus on pre-selected ICT domains and close monitoring to those areas where gaps and impacts emerge.

This will be achieved through a coordinated activity, involving the Project Partners and the External Advisory Group who offer both consolidated expertise in standards, and active involvement in standards committees and bodies, ensuring that information is relevant and timely. Further, collaboration will be sought with SDO’s and other relevant Associations in the form of Memorandum of Understandings to uphold and foster closer relationships.

An enhanced methodology to release the “*Landscape Analysis Reports*” will be executed, to broaden the scope of the already published ones (7) under the previous project (tackling Artificial Intelligence, Trusted Information, Digital Twins, Smart Cities, Cloud for Data, Internet of Things, Edge Computing²). The Consortium will leverage the consolidate partnership with several Standards organisations, PPPs and Research & Innovation Clusters (turned into the signature of +25 Memorandum of Understanding under StandICT.eu 2023, as displayed in *Figure 1* in Section 2.3), in order to introduce a larger peer-review process, carried out by an external and independent community (that will be obviously acknowledged in the new reports). This will bring a tangible added value and will provide the reports a different standpoint from a variety of Stakeholders operative in the field, by including also the new regulatory requirements. Moreover, the overall format of the Reports will be re-designed with the inclusion of a comprehensive and content-driven analysis of the addressed field, on top of the usual and complete Standards mapping. The ultimate scope of the new EUOS (and correlated Reports) moves far beyond being a simple Standard repository and to turn into the “go-to-place” for the ICT Standards community to promote:

- Effective discussion and exchange of information on timely topics though the possibility to join and create discussion groups dedicated to specific fields;
- Comprehensive “*Landscape & Gap analysis*” documents obtained directly from the relative Standards organisations to ensure a complete mapping of the most important trends in ICT domains, as well as ‘novelties’ or specific challenges to be tackled;

² <https://www.standict.eu/landscape-analysis-reports>

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

standICT.eu²⁰²⁶

ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

- A showcase of the results achieved through the StandICT.eu Fellowship Programme;
- An updated list of StandICT.eu-led events as well as third-party events.

A series of four Landscape Analysis to complete is already scheduled for 2023, listed as follows:

- Technical Working Group on Digital Product Passport;
- Technical Working Group on Robotics;
- Technical Working Group on Ontologies;
- Technical Working Group on Blockchain.

Additionally, new TWGs will be rebooted and launched, in compliance with the suggestions provided by the European Commission and the internal EAG, namely:

- Technical Working Group on Cybersecurity;
- Technical Working Group on Big Data Spaces and Data interoperability;
- Technical Working Group on Quantum Technologies;
- Technical Working Group on Intelligent Computing;
- Technical Working Group on Trusted & Secure Chips.

2.3 StandICT.eu Network & Synergies

StandICT.eu 2026 aims to establish (through the deployment of an effective engagement mechanism) a vast and influential network through strategic synergies with ongoing initiatives both at European and global level, to secure and tap into the wide range of competencies and skills needed to provide the required international breadth to the Project. The primary goal is to engage and animate relevant standardisation stakeholders, with specific attention to SMEs, industry verticals, research and academia.

This will be pursued through the wide range of activities envisaged within WP5 and WP6 and it will aim at achieving the following outputs:

- Concrete involvement and continuous alignment with European and International SDOs with the objective of:
 - Promoting the opportunities offered by the Open Calls among the respective ICT Communities;
 - Disseminating the impact attained through the work carried out by the funded experts;
 - Putting the released “Landscape analysis reports” into spotlight and be distributed in contextualised network of professionals and experts;
 - Identifying and pointing out emerging topics, priorities and/or challenges requiring further research, to be timely incorporated in the Open Calls priority list.
- Long-lasting connections with National Standard Bodies to obtain a complete mapping of the different national perspectives and bring up potential ICT Policy development or priorities towards a more Eurocentric approach.

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

- Strengthened partnerships with main actors of the European SMEs ecosystem through a series of agreements to be reached with the associations representing the interests of European SMEs in Standardisation, with the ambitious and dual goal of reinforcing SME presence in the international ICT Standardisation landscape, while feeding the EUOS with the crucial input of small businesses. StandICT.eu can already count on a consolidated relationship with Small Business Standards (SBS) and SMEunited (resulted in the signature of a Memorandum of Understanding).
The biggest added value under the new project is the onboarding of the European Digital SME Alliance as part of the Consortium. DSME is the largest network of ICT small and medium enterprises in Europe (representing more than 45,000 enterprises) with a prominent and permanent position in critical Standardisation-driven for a at EU level such as the High-Level forum on Standardisation, the EC MSP and the Task Force on the Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation. This will be instrumental to adequately decipher and address topics of general interest to ICT small and medium enterprises in Europe as well as to understand SMEs role in the standardisation process.
- Synergies with similar initiatives including European funded Research & Innovation projects (H2020, Horizon Europe or DEP).
- Concerted effort to develop, nurture and extend continuous synergies with European PPPs (ADRA, AI-on-Demand/AI4Europe, ECSO, Big Data Value PPP, 5G PPP, 6G SNS Joint Undertaking, High Performance Computing PPP, Factories of the Future PPP, euRobotics PPP, Quantum Flagship, SOvereignEdge.eu).

StandICT.eu has already a series of ongoing collaborations (framed either under the form of Memorandum of Understanding(s) or cross-project collaborations) to build on and broaden, to ensure optimal visibility of the projects' main outputs across key European organisations and associations.

Figure 1 below presents an updated (at the moment of writing) overview of the organisations, projects and initiatives with active collaboration.

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call	 ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe
Grant Agreement No.: 101091933	

FIGURE 1 - SNAPSHOT OF CURRENT STANDICT.EU NETWORK AND SYNERGIES

2.4 Standards Academy Programme – The Educational side

Standards education will be an integral part of the initiative with the major objective of Improve the expertise and skills and knowledge in standardisation strategy and uptake of European experts of EU organisations involved in international ICT standardisation. The key part of this effort will be implemented under WP4 “Standards Academy Programme” by integrating the previous work undertaken in the remit of StandICT.eu 2023 about standardisation and also materials from national, European and international standardisation bodies.

The activity will be aimed at scoping out the most significant education initiatives available from National Standards Bodies, by exploiting existing synergies and linkage with SDOs and tapping into the knowledge of successful applicants of the Fellowship Programme, with a view to storing these and making them publicly accessible on the platform.

Development of targeted training packages (aimed at reaching out beginners and advanced users) is foreseen plus the delivery and organisation of 5 Courses/Workshops to tackle different ICT Standardisation themes. In order to achieve a satisfactory promotion of the Academy, the Consortium can rely on solid connection with sectoral organisations/entities directly involved in the support of Education in Standardisation, most relevant of which are EURAS (*European Academy for Standardisation*) and Cen/Cenelec STAIR Working Group (through the prominent role of Knut Blind as chair), critical networks to further supporting the development and professionalisation of standards education.

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call	 ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe
Grant Agreement No.: 101091933	

The continuous feeding of the Education section of the EUOS is intended to secure the long-term objective of providing increased awareness and training on standardisation procedures, policy and processes.

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

3. STAKEHOLDER GROUPS

3.1 National Standard Bodies

National Standardisation Bodies represent the benchmark for all stakeholders and the focal point of access to the concerted system, which comprises regional (European) and international standardisation. Within the new framework envisaged in the High-Level Forum, NSBs will also play an important role to shape a new mechanism to share information, coordinate and strengthen the European approach to international standardisation as well as to bring more alignment between European policy priorities, industrial innovation and investment activities and Standardisation actions.

StandICT.eu can already rely on a consolidated synergy established with multiple NSBs across the former projects' editions, that resulted in the formal signature of mutual support agreements [*specifically with National Standards Authority of Ireland (NSAI), Austrian Standards International (ASI), Romanian Standards Association (ASRO), Bureau de Normalisation (NBN), Italian Association for Standardisation (UNI), Spanish Association for Standardisation (UNE) and Standards Norway (SN)*]. However, a continuous and productive relationship is established with all MSs NSBs boards with a view to promote and disseminate the projects' outputs and opportunities across the correlated national communities of experts.

Throughout the whole projects' lifetime, the national associations of the European MSs will be timely and strategically reached out to attain the crucial objectives of the overall Communication plan, listed as follows:

- To act as national/regional sounding board to convey the opportunities of StandICT.eu towards the respective national networks of ICT Standard specialists.
- To contribute to an exhaustive mapping of different requirements across priority ICT areas, with a view to ensure a proper promotion of the European interests and influence on a global scale in the Standardisation arena.
- To support the organisation of joint meetings, events and/or workshops.
- To support the promotion of the Standards Academy Programme and educational activities and raise awareness of the importance of Education in Standardisation.

3.2 European & International SDOs

One of the foundational goals of StandICT.eu is to build upon (and expand) its engaged and relevant community of ICT Standardisation experts, confirming that the project is capable to exploit the consolidated community achieved under the former editions [StandICT.eu & StandICT.eu 2023].

Through the support of an active set of representatives of SDO Working Group, Technical Committee, Focus and Specification Groups, the provision of accurate, timely and up-to-date

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call	 ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe
Grant Agreement No.: 101091933	

information will be made available to spark interaction and debate around rising ICT topics to be potentially fed into the Open Call process.

StandICT.eu will also set-up and continuously maintain a dedicated Database of Contacts to map the complete ecosystem of SDOs with touchpoints identified with the respective Head managers or Head of Communication to ensure additional visibility and a proper outreach of the projects' results, impact and key events.

SDOs shall be implicitly interested in acting as natural amplifier of the initiative (as proven in the past projects), since they can benefit of the Cascading Grants process with the possibility to freely benefit of additional expertise and support from competent specialists that can offer their help to:

- Better understand how to develop Standards capable of effectively impact Industry, Verticals, policies, industry, environment and facilitate the transition towards energy efficiency.
- Close the gap between European priorities and arising ICT Standardisation technologies.
- Bring valuable inputs with a view to speed up an improved alignment and coordination among European and international SDOs, to achieve a shared (or as close as possible) vision on primary ICT technological domains in Standardisation.

The image below (*Figure 2*) provides a snapshot of some of the European and International SDOs and correlated Stakeholders involved with different extent in sectoral ICT fields that we engage with and with whom closer bonds will be forged through systematic, timely and regular engagement, in pursuit of the communication and dissemination objectives of the project, which will take the form of the following activities:

- Direct liaison with Chairs and Co-chairs of Working Groups and Technical Committees also by exploiting the connections of the EAG members (to embark them in virtual or physical events, to ask for support to identify important novelties, gaps or challenges in the relative ICT fields that could feed into the Open Call priorities' list or to join as active members in the various TWGs and contribute to the release of tailored "Landscape Analysis Report").
- Recruit experienced evaluators, especially in those areas where the project can encounter a shortage of available ones.
- Search for opportunities of visibility at PPPs related events (like the EBDV Forum, or 3GPP, or 5GPP & SNS JU, or euRobotics, ESFRI, or EFFRA, ECSO).

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

FIGURE 2 - OVERVIEW OF THE CURRENT NETWORK OF ENGAGED INTERNATIONAL, REGIONAL SDOS AND STANDARDISATION ORGANISATIONS.

3.3 SMEs

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are the backbone of the European economy, comprising 99% of companies and responsible of 67% of employment. Standardisation has a direct impact on their national, European, and global activities since open standards are the tools to adopt and streamline technologies, avoid lock-ins, strengthen competition, and eliminate barriers to trade.

Involvement of SMEs in Standardisation is threefold:

1. As users,
2. As Standards setters,
3. As contributors to standardisation policies.

DSME's WG Standards is a platform that connects SME standardisation experts interested and active in standards setting and policies. It also extends to other working groups at DSME to connect with SMEs that are typically the users of standards. As such it can collect input of the issues regarding standardisation and channel it through experts to the relevant TCs and management groups. WG Standards would be the idle vehicle to disseminate information and objectives of StandICT.eu. As such StandICT.eu will be an outstanding agenda item during the WG meetings and its mailing list will also be utilised to share information, consultations, and general feedback to and from SMEs.

Also, all communication channels at DSME will be utilised to promote access to Standardisation through StandICT.eu, especially with regard to: Calls for funding, standards education (training), and consultations.

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call	 ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe
Grant Agreement No.: 101091933	

In addition, as a founder member of SBS, and a member of smeUnited, where StandICT.eu have established cooperation, DSME can extend to more SMEs when necessary to provide an inclusive process and ensure that what is taking place on the ground is reflected and taken into consideration at standardisation bodies.

3.4 Policy Makers

This group includes stakeholders both at a National and European Level that steer policy priorities towards a more Europe-centred approach in line with the key objectives as defined within the European Strategy on Standardisation, with the topical goal to uphold the shaping of coming (and needed) standardisation policy in different areas (also through the dedicated work of the EUOS TWGs), support the identification of annual priorities, identify future standardisation needs, and provide recommendations on how to better bring closer academia and research with standardisation.

For StandICT.eu, a vital policy stakeholder is the European Commission with its multiple EC directorates and corresponding entities. The Consortium Partners have established and meaningful relationships with Directorates such as DG CONNECT, DG RTD, DG GROW and the REA Research Executive Agency through their involvement in intertwined H2020/Horizon Europe Innovation and Coordination Support Actions. It's worthy of mention that the project managed to cement a long-lasting and open relationship with the EC MSP, whose quarterly meetings are attended by our representatives to report on the main outputs, takeaways and future plans (as well as to integrate feedback coming from the MSPs' members to be fed into the project). A prominent objective of the new initiative will be the establishment of a connection with the High-level forum On Standardisation to better tackle horizontal issues such as education and skills, pre-normative challenges and alignment between European policy priorities, industrial innovation, research activities and standardisation actions (the role of DSME in the "Sherpa" sub-group can facilitate this process).

StandICT.eu will also invite policy officers (as happened in the previous editions) to partake and attend the External Advisory Group, to ensure a constant dialogue between the European Commission and the Project, which through its continuous interaction across national and international SDOs is able to pinpoint topics that require further research and provide coordinated guidance to steer policy priorities.

3.5 Standards Education

Standardisation education is a critical component of the European Commission's approach to strengthening the standardisation interoperability pillar of the Digital Single Market by supporting the creation of tomorrows standards leaders and ensuring that European values are represented in the development of international standards.

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

StandICT.eu has expanded on its role in Standards Education (the EUOS Standards Academy <https://standict.eu/euos-academy>) from the collection, categorisation and annotation existing of standards training material from various sources including ISO, IEC, and ETSI, and in various formats including papers, slides and video content. The new EUOS Standards Education Group (EUOS-SEG) will include key experts from the original Standards Academy (including **Brian McAuliffe** - Chair of EUOS Standards Academy, **Ray Walshe** - EUOS Director, **Ivana Mijatović** - Professor University of Belgrade, **Knut Blind** - Professor TU Berlin) and new members to the EUOS-SEG **Sandra Drechsler**, **Nikolaos Myrionis** - NATO Standardization Management Group/Education Panel and **Joel Myers** - Co-Chair of the IEEE Internet of Things (IoT) Consortium Smart Cities Working Group. The group will be chaired by Professor Knut Blind of Fraunhofer. These experts will help create training material at beginner and advanced levels to deliver training workshops to engage a wider stakeholder ecosystem in standardisation.

Thus, the EUOS-SEG will deliver key exploitable results for the future generation of ICT standardisation experts by (a) increased participation of SMEs, StartUps through workshops, and webinars (b) 1000+ beginners, advanced trained participants on standardisation and (c) developing a sustainable StandICT.eu resource of training material for reuse in future standard initiatives.

3.6 Open Source Community

Open source is not new to the world of Standardisation, and neither are standards too distanced from open source. Over the past years, SDOs have initiated a number of activities on open sources' software. Such activities take different forms and address different aspects. Open source and standardisation exchanges range from simple exchanges of methodologies (understanding the ways of working and integrating Open Source mechanisms into standardisation) to SDOs using Open Source as a mechanism to provide reference implementations of a specific standard or standards based architecture. In recent years, however, collaboration between the two ecosystems could arguably go further. For example, how can OSS communities participate in the creation of standards that take place in SDOs? And how can projects in the OSS community transfer their results to SDOs for further formalisation?

Another reason it is important for StandICT.eu to strengthen these linkages between open source and Standardisation is the general trend of more and more de facto standards coming in the form of Open Source projects.

StandICT.eu will create a platform to exchange further between the two communities. In open source, the first place to start the exchange is the OSS foundations. These range from the

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call	 ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe
Grant Agreement No.: 101091933	

large ones, such as the *Linux Foundation*³, the *Eclipse Foundation*⁴ and the *Apache Software Foundation*⁵. Interestingly, there are specific developments related to Europe that the standardisation ecosystem should be aware of, such as the move of the Eclipse Foundation to become a European entity, and the recent launch of the Linux Foundation Europe.

Another example of a stakeholder to engage with are the *Joint Development Foundation*⁶, a project under the Linux Foundation for collaborative creation of technical specifications and standards.

3.7 H2020, Horizon Europe projects and other R&I initiatives

StandICT.eu will target European research and innovation projects and innovation initiatives carried out at national levels, which are related to the horizontal and vertical ICT sectors. We will start building this stakeholder group on the actors engaged in StandICT.eu 2023, with the goal to reach out to an increasing number of projects that, as a part of their research, aim at contributing to the international ICT Standardisation. To accomplish this goal, we will use the partners' strong involvement in various projects and consortia. In addition, the funded fellows are frequently linked to diverse research initiatives that will be also connected to the StandICT.eu community.

The engagement of this stakeholder group will cover namely the following activities:

- Recruitment of contributing members to the EUOS TWGs and WGs.
- Promotion of the Open Calls to find new applicants and fellows.
- Participation in the Walk & Talk webinars.
- Involvement in the draft and elaboration of Landscape reports, Fellowship Impact report, and other major publications.
- Search opportunities to increase StandICT.eu visibility within their communities, and vice-versa. Essentially, using their social media and websites to promote the StandICT.eu Open Calls, events and results.

Moreover, StandICT.eu has already established a collaboration with two major CSA project funded under Horizon Europe Programme;

³ <https://www.linuxfoundation.org/>

⁴ <https://www.eclipse.org/>

⁵ <https://www.apache.org/>

⁶ <https://jointdevelopment.org/>

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

- **HS Booster**⁷ that provides tailored and professional guidance to H2020 and Horizon Europe projects to carry out Standardisation-related activities and to better map and understand the correlated Standards' ecosystem.
- **Stand4EU**⁸ that foster the EU contribution to the international Standardisation, especially in the field of manufacturing.

The figure below gives a snapshot of the already engaged cross-initiative collaborations, and more will be scouted and contacted throughout the project. Moreover, some of these projects will arrive to their end, in consequence it is even more important to scout new related initiatives.

FIGURE 3 - STANDICT.EU'S NETWORK OF EUROPEAN PROJECTS' SYNERGIES

⁷ <https://hsbooster.eu/>

⁸ www.stand4eu.eu/

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

4. OPEN CALL(S) PROMOTIONAL STRATEGY

4.1 Open Call for Evaluators

StandICT.eu will recruit a group of external, independent experts to evaluate the proposals submitted to the Open Calls in order to form a pool of (at least) 50 professional evaluators (EPE). The Open Call to recruit the EPE will be launched by the end of M3 (March 2023).

The Consortium will also benefit from the already existing list of experts from the current pool, that will be personally invited to re-submit an application with the objective to fulfil any shortage of experts in specific domains and tackle any new Standardisation priority that's should arise. The Experts will be categorised under various ICT standardisation areas, for their allocation and matching to an applicant Project according to their expertise. Each expert will evaluate a range of 8 to 10 proposals per evaluation cycle: more specifically every proposal will undergo the evaluation of 3 different experts, of which one will be the rapporteur with the introduction of the role of the "Quality Controller" who will perform the final overall check.

A dedicated (optional) "reserve Call" is envisaged throughout the course of the projects' lifecycle in case of retiring members that need to be replaced or/if new areas (uncovered at the moment of the launch of the opening call) should emerge.

Additionally, the Open call for evaluators will be also exhaustively promoted across the complete spectrum of the projects' network, with a major focus towards NSBs and sectoral SDOs committees, working groups and focus groups.

FIGURE 4 – OFFICIAL BANNER OF EPE OPEN CALL

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call	 ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe
Grant Agreement No.: 101091933	

4.2 Open Call for Applicants/Experts

Each Open Call will undergo a thorough and intensive promotional phase, where the communication and engagement activities will be focused on prompting ICT Standards specialists to participate in the Open Calls, and a dissemination phase dedicated to showcasing the results derived from the funded proposals.

The first Open Call promotional campaign will pave the way for the others to follow, with activities continuously monitored and compared with the results attained in terms of applications received, ICT areas covered and Standards organisations addressed by the submitted proposals.

The Open Call promotional campaigns presented in this document aim at achieving the following goals:

- Raise awareness of the StandICT.eu project and the expected results;
- Keep the community continuously informed on the progress and the results of the Open Calls and broad dissemination of information that facilitate and support new applications for the future calls;
- High visibility and full coverage among the primary stakeholders to make sure that the maximum number of EU SMEs and companies, R&D organisations, Research Centres, Industry sector organisations & Clusters can benefit of the calls' opportunity;
- Dissemination of the 9 "Impact Reports" to put spotlights on the main outputs attained by the funded fellows to demonstrate the tangible results of their Standardisation-related activities, in tackling priorities, gaps and challenges of correlated ICT areas.

In order to reinforce the brand recognition and to further consolidate the projects' visual identity among the community, a vibrant visual approach will be adopted as part of the communication strategy: Open Calls' themes will follow the style of the previous edition, all inspired by nature (to point out even more the crucial role played by technological Standards to overcome the vital challenges defined by the "European Green Deal" in terms of sustainable economic growth, climate neutral continent and energy efficiency) and will characterise the communication of the entire project during the period relative to the corresponding Open Call (*Figure 5*). Each image will be also accompanied by meaningful (and contextualised) quotes from authoritative personalities to bolster the importance of the addressed subjects.

Open Calls' promotion will be dutifully synchronised with the EC for their timely and smooth support of the respective open calls.

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

FIGURE 5 - FIRST OPEN CALL THEMATIC BANNER

5. METHODOLOGY BEHIND THE COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND ENGAGEMENT PLAN

5.1 Branding and Visual Identity guidelines

The project can rely on the already solidified visual identity built throughout the previous projects' cycles and that heavily contributed to the community's widening

Seamless and uniform templates for external communication and documents will also be provided to the Consortium, with a view to deliver a consistent message to the wide diversity of audiences that the project will talk to. The corporate identity of StandICT.eu includes also the EU emblem, showing clearly that this is an EU-funded CSA.

As a result of this homogeneous and solid Branding strategy, the project aims to achieve the following goals:

- Improved recognition and acknowledgement across a broad range of Stakeholders.
- Strengthened loyalty and trust from the audience.
- Continuity of the overall StandICT.eu message conveyed across the main communication sources and assets such as:
 - Website
 - Social Media channels
 - Branded giveaways
 - Interviews or/and audio visuals
 - Press Releases
 - Impact Reports
 - Landscape Analysis Reports
 - Marketing collaterals (flyers, brochures, posters, RollUp Banners)
 - Press Release(s)
 - Letterhead

Adhering to specific imagery and visual (agreed) guidelines is fundamental for the project to establish a direct connection with the project objectives and goals and the audience to target, with a view to attain the following results:

- To establish a visible connection between the project's content and the communication materials;
- To help the audience resonate with the project's communication and dissemination actions and making goals and overall message crystal clear;
- To easily identify the project during both virtual and/or real events;
- To establish a liaison between visual elements and the wording used to showcase the project across different platforms and sources (social media, web, offline media and print).

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call	 ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe
Grant Agreement No.: 101091933	

FIGURE 6 - OFFICIAL STANDICT.EU & EUOS LOGOS

Main usage of the logo - The logo should always be shown as clearly as possible and must not be overwhelmed by other visual elements. The logo and its components must never be altered or modified in any way. The logo is most effective when positioned on a clear background, which helps to protect its integrity. The logo should always be used in full. The logo should never be moved or adjusted.

Document templates for external communication have also been set-up. The rationale behind this strategy is to guarantee a streamlined communication style and provide the entire StandICT.eu Consortium with a shared toolkit of Communication tools to be utilised in recurring situations, events, deliveries or formal exchanges to outreach specific target audiences (Figures 8, 9, 10). All templates will be safely stored and completely accessible for the Consortium members in the shared repository (Google Drive), as carefully described in “D1.1 Project Handbook”.

StandICT.eu 2026 |

 Grant Agreement No.: 101091933 Call: HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01
Type of action: CSA

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DX.X Deliverable Title

Work package	
Task	
Due date	
Submission date	
Deliverable lead	
Version	
Authors	
Reviewers	

Executive Summary	Included
Keywords	

FIGURE 7 – DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE

FIGURE 8 – POWERPOINT PPT TEMPLATE

PRESS RELEASE - StandICT.eu continues its journey until 2026

StandICT.eu now in its sixth year, held the first physical kick-off meeting in Paris from 8-9th February 2023, to officially launch activities under the new Grant Agreement. StandICT.eu 2026, with the European Commission for the continuation of the Coordination and Support Action with a new and ambitious Work Programme to take it through to January 2026 in support of the European Standardisation Strategy, released in February 2022 and following the creation of the High-Level Expert Group on European Standardisation, which has brought Standardisation activities to the forefront of the agenda in Europe. Standards, and in particular ICT standards, play a key role in enabling the interoperability of new technologies, which brings significant benefits both for a wide range of industries and also supports an increasing number of domains in non-ICT fields.

The new StandICT.eu initiative is managed by a lean yet strengthened consortium, comprising: **StandICT (IT)**, coordinator of the two predecessor projects - leading communication and dissemination activities and managing the open call programme, together with **Dublin City University (IE)** - leading the EUOS and the **Technical Working Groups and AUSTRALGO (IE)** - managing the workings of the StandICT.eu Fellows and ensuring their impact towards the EU. These new players are joining the field to further reinforce the Consortium and bring fresh expertise: the **European Digital SME Alliance** - which will deliver SME guidelines and support through a mentoring programme, **Quantum Europe** which will address Open Standards and Open Software and bring a new network in the open source industry, and the **European Digital Skills Alliance** who through the role of **Knut Strand**, Chair of the **Con-Canonic STAR Working Group**, will place the Consortium in the perfect position to address any matter related to integrating Standardisation with innovation, research and education.

The new project will move beyond the usual tasks of its open calls created from the ICT Rolling Plan for Standardisation to address ongoing trends discussed in international Standardisation Committees and here, in this respect, the StandICT.eu Fellows are expected to play an ever more important role in bringing a European perspective to the international standardisation setting and to contribute to the development of standards in full compliance with European values, policies and regulations.

The activity of the EUOS will continue with the release of new and more comprehensive landscape analysis reports, in key and emerging domains and with a new emphasis on the meaningful analysis of the broader range of knowledge and data gathered through increased involvement of the community network (FPs, Fellows, PPPs and R&D projects) to generate a thorough overview.

In this context, StandICT.eu initiatives has been funded by the European Commission for an additional 3-year period, with the primary goal of ensuring tangible support to the community of European ICT experts in pursuit of the EU's interests in the international ICT Standardisation ecosystem. The main goal of StandICT.eu 2026 is to strengthen its global reach in the European ICT Standardisation Ecosystem with several supporting actions, which include:

- Launching and managing a robust and efficient facility supporting the Fellowship Programme with € 2,925,000 in funding that will be distributed over 9 Open Calls;
- Strengthening the EUOS (EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation) and the Technical Working Groups (TWGs) empowering contributions from ICT Standardisation experts;
- Training the next generation of ICT Standardisation experts, engaging with National Standardisation Bodies & PPPs;
- Creating and engaging an Industry Forum on EU Strategy for ICT standards to address policy (FOREST), to keep momentum in policy discussions, in-synch with the EC Multi-Stakeholder Platform;
- Supporting and sharing insights with the High-Level Forum on European Standardisation, to which a first set of recommendations was already delivered in January 2023.

11 "What we have observed with StandICT.eu over the past few years, is the sense of "community" around ICT standards that the project has managed to develop and this manifests itself through the ever increasing number of Fellows who apply to our Open Calls, and the enthusiastic contributions to support the Thematic Technical Working Groups. With the dedicated increase in StandICT.eu Academy content, this has put us in an excellent position in 2023 to strengthen these key areas and grow not only the community but rather the project to draw from our experts, prove knowledge and share this Standardisation know-how in a more structured way. We look forward to the next 36 months together with our expanded partnership too! **Silvana Muscato, Technical Coordinator of StandICT.eu 2026 & Trust IT CEO.**

12 "The continuation of the StandICT.eu brand into 2026 with an expanded partner network can now deliver an strategic and policy, and experts support and training to provide EU Leadership in international Standardisation. This ecosystem building of the next generation of European standards professionals will increase our leadership potential in emerging technology domains and increase the presence of EU values in international standards development". **Ray Walsh, Financial Coordinator of StandICT.eu 2026 & EUOS Director, from DCU**

13

The Fellowship Programme

2,925,000 Millions € available through 9 Open Calls for European ICT Standards experts (400+)

A pool of 50+ External Evaluators

to ensure a fair and transparent Open Call process

Training & Education

Skills Training Workshops, Webinars & the Standards Training Academy

FOREST

"Forum for European Strategy on ICT Standards" to help increase EU leadership in international standards activities

How to get involved

- Apply to one of our open calls and get funded to support your work in the ICT Standardisation field. We have just closed our 9th (and last) Open call under the remit of StandICT.eu 2023. The first Open Call under StandICT.eu 2026, will open in May 2023.
- Submit your success story about the impact your work in Standardisation has concretely produced and receive recognition for this across our community.
- Consult our EUOS Standards Repository and contribute to our open discussions.
- Learn more about standards relying on the content of our ICT Standards Academy and the Landscape Analysis Reports, prepared by our Technical Working Groups.

Who's behind StandICT.eu 2026

StandICT.eu 2026 Consortium:
Dublin City University (IE) - Financial and Administrative Coordinator, Trust-IT SH (IT) - Technical Coordinator, OpenForum Europe (BE), AUSTRALGO (ES), European Digital SME Alliance (BE), and Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research (DE).

For more information on StandICT.eu 2026, contact us at info@standict.eu and follow us on our social media channels: Twitter | LinkedIn | YouTube

StandICT.eu 2026 has received funding from the EU's Horizon Europe Programme under Grant Agreement no. 101091933.

FIGURE 9 - PRESS RELEASE EXAMPLE FROM PROJECTS' KO MEETING9

⁹ Extended version <https://www.standict.eu/news/press-release-standicteu-2026>

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

5.2 Webinars & Workshops

The organisation of a series of Webinars (18) and Workshops (5) will be crucial from a strategic standpoint to broaden the outreach of the project, to ignite new synergies with other projects that have standardisation as a key-component of their work plan and to effectively promote each Open Call cycle.

Calls will be often accompanied by webinars and workshops co-located with associations, SDO organisations, relevant EU or international initiatives involved in Standardisation, or SMEs networks where possible to spark engagement, provide exhaustive coverage across the different ICT Communities and to gather insights on priorities and/or new trends from different Stakeholders to be possibly fed into the following Open Calls.

These events will be important also to address, to a broader extent, high-profile themes such as European industry competitiveness, the wider impact of sustainability, sovereignty and the green deal by cooperating also with like-minded projects active in the fields of green deal, digital twin, blue economy, circular economy.

The work plan entails the management of 18 Webinars and 5 Workshops: each Webinar should focus on a particular subject, namely the leading topic of the Open Calls, bringing together influential experts of the field. They will also be the ideal spot to present in great detail the final outputs of TWGs and the corresponding "Landscape Analysis Report". Under WP4. 2 Training Skills Workshops and 3 Training Academy Workshops will be carried across the 36 months of the project, aimed at tackling different levels of Standardisation skills.

Hereunder, a list of keynote speakers and guests to be involved in the organisation of this events:

- StandICT.eu Community members and/or funded applicants for the correlated topic(s).
- SDOs members (WG Chairs, Convenors, Co-Chairs).
- Representatives of National Standards Bodies.
- European Commission Policy Officers.
- Representative of SMEs or SMEs organisations.
- EAG and/or EPE members.
- Relevant figures in specific ICT field or coming from the OSS community.

The workflow of each workshop/webinar will follow a precise action plan that can be described as follow:

1. Overall Management of logistical aspects:
 - a. Identify opportunities to set-up (or join) co-located/jointed events.
 - b. Choice of appropriate location.
 - c. Looking for synergies with similar projects/initiatives.
 - d. Shipping of marketing material to the venue.

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

- e. Check the status of technological tools to ensure a perfect running both in hybrid and online mode (audience engagement software, streaming platforms, internet servers and production equipment, cameras, microphones, mixers, lighting etc).
2. Guests and Speakers recruiting.
3. Preparation of a time-schedule for the event.
4. Publicity/promotion - both through online and off-line campaigns:
 - a. Dedicated web page and online promotion.
 - b. Events calendars.
 - c. Printed programs.
 - d. Media relations and showcase on third-party channels.
 - e. Email Campaign to address all the Stakeholders touchpoints and the whole StandICT.eu community.
 - f. Social Media Plan interlinking all the Social Media channels inclusive of dedicated banners/headers, promotion through professional groups on LinkedIn, creation of Event page(s), event hashtag, branded graphics with personalised cards featuring the Speakers, live-tweet and coverage during the event.
 - g. LinkedIn Event feature to reach out the entire spectrum of LinkedIn's connections.
5. Follow-Up activities
 - a. Timely update the Webinar/Workshop page in order to make the registration or report of the event available within 24 hours after the conclusion of the event.
 - b. Follow-up article to highlight the key-takeaways of the event.
 - c. Sending any unanswered questions to the speaker to properly get back to the attendees.
 - d. Upload of PPT Presentations of the speakers.
 - e. "Throwback Strategy" on Social Media by repurposing the Webinar/Workshop news in the following weeks in view of the coming one(s) and to gather more viewers even post-event.

In addition to Webinars and Workshops, a series of Virtual Interview/Podcasts could be considered as a mitigation measure in replacement of some webinars, to better emphasize the correlation among the project's objectives and the current evolution of the Standardisation landscape, by involving EAGs' members, funded fellows or members of TWGs from different ICT backgrounds.

As follows, some illustrative samples of the first Webinar of the project will take place on the 28th of April 2023 tackling "[Digital Product Passport - Making informed choices and protecting brands](#)" and featuring the leading roles of the TWG:

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

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WEBINAR

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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

28th April 2023 15:00-16:30 (CEST)

Walk & Talk

Digital Product Passport
Making informed choices and protecting brands

SPEAKERS

- Silvana Muscella
Trust-IT Services CEO & StandICT.eu Coordinator
- Ilias Iakovidis
Adviser, Digital aspects of green transition at European Commission DG CONNECT
- Jens Gayko
Managing Director Standardization Council Industrie 4.0
- Benjamin Helfritz
Head of Quality in Transformation at DIN Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V.
- Susanne Guth-Orlowski
Chief Innovation & Solution Officer at Spherity
- Francesca Poggiali
Chief Public Policy Officer Europe at GS1
- Thomas L. Rödding
Entrepreneur, Digitalist & Strategist at Narravero

powered by **EUOS**
EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation

FIGURE 10 – PROMOTIONAL BANNER OF THE FIRST STANDICT.EU 2026'S WEBINAR

5.3 Social Media channels

Ongoing management and nurturing of social media networks like Twitter (@Stand_ICT), LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/standict-eu/>) and relevant groups within it is central to the StandICT.eu communication plan, leveraging the already engaged and extensive community built across the former projects' editions.

Continuous online presence through prominent social networks will try to inform, guide and solicit standards specialists and standards organisations to prepare and submit applications on the one hand, and showcase opportunities for participation/contributions on the other.

It is equally important to keep the web platform animated with content of direct interest to stakeholders, feeding into social media activities, which require constant updating to be a real success. At the same time, in each media the corresponding content will be attentively customized to fit the "rules" of each social media platform.

- Twitter will be mostly exploited for keeping the community up to speed on ICT standardisation, open call opportunities and impacts, also from the EU policy perspective, microblogging and present a "teaser" of the most significant outputs (such coming events, sharing of Impact and Landscape analysis reports, Success stories).

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

Insights from standards experts and market analysts are also a key feature of the social media strategy. Twitter will also be the perfect platform to provide real-time coverage of digital and hybrid event through streaming features and/or live-tweeting for the benefit of the community.

As follows, some meaningful examples of the most relevant connections that encompasses National Standards Bodies, European and International SDOs, Professional and Industry networks and SMEs associations, PPPs and Horizon Europe/H2020 funded projects: *Oasis Open, SFS Finnish Standards Associations, 5GAA, ETUC Standards, Standards Council of Canada, IEEE Standards Association, DIN Germany, UNE Asociación Española de Normalización, SIS - Svenska institutet för standarder, IEC Standards, ATOS Cybersecurity, ERCIM, ENISA, W3C Developers, AFNOR, oneM2M, Open Forum Europe, StartUp EU, National Standards Authority of Ireland – NSAI, Austrian Standards ASI, ANEC, CEN/CENELEC, Big Data Value, Open Grid Forum, Small Business Standards – SBS, ECSO, INATBA, INFINITECH, AIOTI, Digital Europe, AI for Good, Blockchain Skills for Europe, IBM Europe Policy, EU Blockchain, NGI4EU, EC Software and Cloud, CTTC, ITU Standardization, EPOS.*

- LinkedIn is an essential professional network for StandICT.eu, both to broaden its own community and to leverage consolidated networks within the consortium, bringing the most relevant connections onboard the project's community. LinkedIn groups are also an important channel for reaching a broad base for the open calls, adapting to identified priorities and new ones emerging during the project lifecycle. LinkedIn is also by far the most important building block of the overall StandICT.eu Social media strategy, accounting more than 3500 members at the moment (size that results in a favourable opportunity of promotion and dissemination of every output and result).

LinkedIn will also play a fundamental role in promoting events through the exploitation of the LinkedIn Events functionalities that will facilitate the engagement of each individual of the community to join any kind of event (online workshops, webinars).

As follows, a sample of the most influential groups to be leveraged on LinkedIn where StandICT.eu is already an active member: *IEEE Robotics & Automation Society (48.000 members), IEEE Computer Society (33.000 members), Cybersecurity Europe (5.000 members), European Data Protection Forum - EDPF (17.000 members), Europe's Digital Agenda Initiative (4.000 members), Next Generation Internet – NGI (11.000 members), IEEE Internet of Things (7.300 members), 3GPP 5G NR Standards (12.000 members), The Big Data Institute (14.000 members), ETSI People (2.000 members), Digital Europe (11.000 members), ISO/IEC AI (2.000 members), Small Business Standards (1.300 members), 6G SNS (1.300 members), IEEE Communications Society (16.000 members), IEEE Future Networks (1.300 members), World of Standards (1.500 members).*

Other channels will be integrated into the Social Media Plan over the course of the project, such as YouTube to showcase short video clips on StandICT.eu and its community of domain experts and specialists. Zenodo¹⁰ will be the open repository of the projects where all the main

¹⁰ https://zenodo.org/communities/standict_eu/?page=1&size=20

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

reports and publications will be collected with a publicly available Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to make the upload easily and uniquely citeable (and findable).

The overall graphical layout will adhere to the evolved branding that will be chosen for each of the Open Calls and/or to bolster the promotion of coming events/released outputs. You can see below a snapshot of the Social Media graphics selected to put the release of the last TWG Landscape Analysis report into spotlight (in the example the Twitter header):

FIGURE 11 – EXAMPLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA LAYOUT TO SUPPORT PROMOTION OF SPECIFIC OUTPUTS

5.4 Newsletters

StandICT.eu will regularly send newsletters to its subscribers to inform them of the project's activities and status of the Open Calls, to engage them, and to share events and dissemination material.

In the StandICT.eu communication funnel the newsletter plays a pivotal role in building users' loyalty. The image below shows a visual example of an email newsletter that reflects the brand identity of the project and ends with a clear call to action. It represents the standard structure used for all Newsletters' issues.

To make newsletters more visually appealing, and in order to strengthen the StandICT.eu brand, newsletters will mirror the graphic style of the ongoing Open Call. Newsletter's release will be scheduled at least on a monthly basis (*expected KPI: 36 issues by M36*). The issues' frequency can be enhanced in conjunction with specific and important events (like Webinars, Workshops or participation to third-party events/conferences) in order both to increase the recruitment of new participants or to deliver "takeaway messages". The series of webinars and events will be instrumental to enhance the overall amount of newsletter subscribers.

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

Below an example of the Standards layout of StandICT.eu Newsletter ([here the dedicated website area](#)):

FIGURE 12 - EXAMPLE OF STANDICT.EU NEWSLETTER (FEBRUARY 2023 ISSUE)

5.5 Third-party events

Positioning the project inside the wide standardisation ecosystems is a task that will require constant effort and engagement actions with relevant stakeholders. Among several activities that will be carried out, the participation in third party events will play a crucial role in the achievement of this goal. Identification of the most relevant events will be regularly discussed during the monthly PMB meeting as well as within WPs' dedicated calls. The events will be carefully selected in order to attend and partake the ones whose topic coverage, Stakeholders and possibilities to establish connections with SDOs or similar initiatives are aligned with the current goals of the project.

Overall objectives can be instead listed as follows:

- Continuously improve dialogues with policy, research, industry and SDOs.
- Foster multi-stakeholder perspectives to help create synergies and build consensus on the chosen topics.
- Find effective ways of lowering the entry barriers for participation and contributions, thus helping to transfer research results to the standardisation process and increase the effective participation of European specialists in international ICT standardisation activities.
- Identify the standards organisations with on-going or planned standardisation work on the priority topics.

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

As follows, a preliminary list of the identified opportunities for the first 12 months of the project, where StandICT.eu could look for additional visibility, a physical/virtual presence or to organise co-located workshops/panels:

- EC Multi-Stakeholder Platform (March) and 2023s' meetings
- Cen Cenelec STAIR (March) and 2023s' meeting
- The ETSI Seminar (June)
- ETSI EUCnC and 6g Summit (June)
- EURAS and SIIT Conference (June)
- ENISA AI Cybersecurity Conference (June)
- Data Week 2023 (June)
- Digital Europe Summer Summit (June)
- World Circular Economy Forum (June)
- International Symposium on Transportation Data & Modelling EC JRC (June)
- IEEE Workshop on Smart Circular Economy (June)
- Blockchain Skills Conference (June)
- EIT Digital: GROW DIGITAL 23 CONFERENCE and other EIT events (June)
- Open Science Festival (July)
- European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference PVSEC - EC JRC (September)
- EU Research & Innovation Days (September)
- ETSI Security Conference (October)
- World Standards Week (October)
- Quantum Industry Summit (October)
- Security Forum 2023 (October)
- Blockchain for Europe Summit (October)
- European Big Data Value Forum EBDVF (October)
- AIOTI Webinar & Digital Events (recurring)

5.6 Timeline of Activities (M1 – M12)

The table below outlines the action plan at the time of writing this report. The Plan plots a core set of activities taking place in M01-12. The plan is considered a living document that will be regularly updated in concert with the StandICT.eu Consortium, detailing specific roles and responsibilities and according specific needs that might arise during the projects' execution (the size and frequency of some activities/events can vary and/or be substituted with different ones).

Timeline	Activity Planned
February 2023 (M2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • StandICT.eu Website adjustment • Kick-Off Press Release (project launch) • Social Media Activity • Elaboration of a Roll-Up banner and Projects' Notepad

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Signature of MoU with Stand4EU project
March 2023 (M3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graphic Material for the #1 Open Call • EPE Open Call Banners • Launch of EPE Open Call • Press Release – Issue of TWG on Digital Product Passport (#1) • Elaboration of Graphic Kit to support the dissemination of DPP Report • Social Media Activity • Participation in MSP Meeting • Attendance Cen Cenelec STAIR Meeting • #1 Newsletter Issue • A stakeholder survey to H2020 / HE Projects on the emerging technologies to be included in the Open Call topics
April 2023 (M4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Running Campaign for Evaluators recruitment • #1 Webinar on DPP and correlated promotion campaign • #3 Third-party event • Social Media Activity • Continue the Campaign towards Horizon/EC funded projects • StandICT.eu Interview video (#1)
May 2023 (M5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch and Campaign of #1 Open Call for Applicants • #2 Newsletter Issue • Social Media Activity • Completion of Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (in coordination with WP5) and outreach to all 7 SGs • Publication of #2 TWG Landscape Analysis Report & correlated graphic/promotional campaign
June 2023 (M6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EURAS Conference (#4 Third-party event) • Training Workshop (#1) • #5 Third-party event • Social Media Activity • General Flyer on Open Calls • StandICT.eu Interview video (#2)
July 2023 (M7)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • #3 Newsletter Issue • Social Media Activity • EC MSP Meeting • #2 Webinar “Women in ICT Standardisation” • StandICT.eu Interview video (#3) • Publication of #3 TWG Landscape Analysis Report & correlated graphic/promotional campaign

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

standICT.eu²⁰²⁶

ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

August 2023 (M8)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch and Campaign of #2 Open call for Applicants • #4 Newsletter Issue • Social Media Activity • StandICT.eu Poster
September 2023 (M9)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • #5 Newsletter Issue • #6 and #7 Third-party event • Social Media Activity • #3 Webinar on Open Calls' Topic/TWG • "StandICT.eu Ambassador" Campaign (with interview or Twitter Cards or blog posts on the new funded experts)
October 2023 (M10)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • #1 Fellows' Impact Report Release • #6 Monthly Newsletter Issue • Social Media Activity • #4 Webinar on Open Calls' Topic/TWG • Launch and Campaign of #3 Open call for Applicants • #8 Third-party event – World Standards Day/Week
November 2023 (M11)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication of #4 TWG Landscape Analysis Report & correlated graphic/promotional campaign • #6 Newsletter Issue • Social Media Activity • Publication #1 Success Study
December 2023 (M12)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • #5 Webinar on Open Calls' Topic/TWG • #7 Newsletter Issue • Social Media Activity

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

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Grant Agreement No.: 101091933

6. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable is meant as a sort of Roadmap and baseline for StandICT.eu 2026's planned activities for communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement (and open call campaigns) for the entire duration of the project. As already mentioned in the Introduction (*section 1.1*), this is a one-off document and not iterations are formally envisaged. Thus, the document needs to be considered as a benchmark for the overall Communication & Dissemination plan, inclusive of the most important assets, tools, channels and methodology that will be leveraged and executed in the following 36 months.

Said this, it's worthy to stress how the document needs to be considered as a living one, that can be easily adapted and updated over time to reflect new priorities identified, such as the Open Call campaigns and related topics, as well as workshop timings and stakeholder focus, necessary to maximise impacts (the issue of an additional mid-term version can also be contemplated).

StandICT.eu has an agile approach to tackle core activities coordinated through WP6. The monthly activity plan is fully integrated in the current Communication and Engagement strategy. It also takes into account project milestones, to keep track of progress towards the work plan, and deliverables, which are also sources for impact and insight pieces for publication on the web platform. Each of the planned actions will always be customised to properly reach out the targeted Stakeholder (as defined in *Section 3*).

The thorough implementation of the dissemination and communication strategy (as described in the deliverable) will contribute to the consolidation of the StandICT.eu identity making the project recognisable, reliable and prominent in relevant ICT areas and communities of experts, leaving a strong legacy and a wide (freely accessible) knowledge hub (the Standards Academy and the EUOS) to tap into for the ICT Standardisation and Research community.

D6.1: Plan for communication & Stakeholder engagement strategy & Plan and promotion of the open call

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